

Article

Incidence of the Flipped Classroom in the Physical Education Students' Academic Performance in University Contexts

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Abstract: This research analyzed Physical Education students' degree of academic performance with the incorporation of active methodologies, specifically flipped classroom mixed learning, restricted to evaluation periods in the months of June and September. The study focused on whether there are significant differences in this variable through the scores obtained. Through a simple random sampling, 131 students participated in this empiric-analytic research, using an ex-post-facto study with a retrospective design with quasi-control group. A robust test of averages comparison, multiple linear regressions and an evaluation of the relative importance of predictors was conducted. The results show how flipped classroom methodology linearly and positively influences academic performance and correlational motivation and support. As main conclusion, in a hybrid and digitalized learning context, the value of the consideration of active methodologies (flipped classroom) based on emerging pedagogies, allows improving students' achievement and competence development, providing critical, significant, ubiquitous, transformational and especially motivating experiences.

Keywords: flipped classroom; methodological change; ICT

1. Introduction

The gap between practice in classrooms and training education in Higher Education requires a transformation of the academic model. This new paradigm includes a shift to hybrid learning with the integration of new tools and methodologies that challenges the educational position of the traditional teaching that has existed for decades at universities for the improvement of the teaching–learning process, providing dynamic and innovative opportunities from active student participation. In this sense, the new Higher Education framework (2010) encourages teachers to integrate technology in the classroom, as it becomes clear in Horizon Report (2016), achieving a significant impact on education in the next three years [1]. To this end, teachers must not only use technological tools, but they should also familiarize themselves with the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model to integrate technology with disciplinary, pedagogical and technological knowledge, offering more interaction between teachers and students [2].

Students are not mere spectators during their learning through the listening processes sitting in class, performing tasks and waiting for the teacher's answers. Students must actively participate on what they are learning, interact and transfer the contents and apply them to contextual situations. One of the teaching–learning processes that is gaining ground in the different educational levels is the B-Learning or mixed learning, defined as the combination of class work and online work with some

1. González-Gómez, D.; Su, J.; Airado, D.; Cañada-Cañada, F. Performance and Perception in the Flipped Learning Model: An Initial Approach to Evaluate the Effectiveness of a New Teaching Methodology in a General Science Classroom. *J. Sci. Educ. Technol.* **2016**, *25*, 450–459. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Mingorance, A.C.; Trujillo, J.M.; Cáceres, P.; Torres, C. Mejora del rendimiento académico a través de la metodología de aula invertida centrada en el aprendizaje activo del estudiante universitario de ciencias de la educación. *J. Sport Health Res.* **2017**, *9*, 129–136.
3. Koo, C.L.; Demps, E.L.; Farris, C.; Bowman, J.D.; Panahi, L.; Boyle, P. Impact of Flipped Classroom Design on Student Performance and Perceptions in a Pharmacotherapy Course. *Am. J. Pharm. Educ.* **2016**, *80*, 1–9. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
4. Sahin, A.; Cavlazoglu, B.; Zeytuncu, Y.E. Flipping a College Calculus Course: A Case Study. *Educ. Technol. Soc.* **2015**, *18*, 142–152.
5. Betihavas, V.; Bridgman, H.; Kornhaber, R.; Cross, M. The evidence for ‘flipping out’: A systematic review of the flipped classroom in nursing education. *Nurse Educ. Today* **2016**, *38*, 15–21. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
6. Geist, M.J.; Larimore, D.; Rawiszer, H.; Al Sager, A.W. Flipped versus traditional instruction and achievement in a baccalaureate nursing pharmacology course. *Nurs. Educ. Perspect.* **2015**, *36*, 114–115. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
7. Yacout, D.; Shosha, A. Nursing students’ perceptions towards flipped classroom educational strategy. *J. Am. Sci.* **2016**, *12*, 62–75. [[CrossRef](#)]
8. Albert, M.; Beatty, B.J. Flipping the classroom applications to curriculum redesign for an introduction to management course: Impact on grades. *J. Educ. Bus.* **2014**, *89*, 419–424. [[CrossRef](#)]
9. Borchardt, J.; Bozer, A.H. Psychology course redesign: An interactive approach to learning in a micro-flipped classroom. *Smart Learn. Environ.* **2017**, *4*, 1–9. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Blair, E.; Maharaj, C.; Primus, P. Performance and perception in the flipped classroom. *Educ. Inf. Technol.* **2016**, *21*, 1465–1482. [[CrossRef](#)]
11. Lin, Y.; Zhu, Y.; Chen, C.; Wang, W.; Chen, T.; Li, T.; Li, Y.; Liu, B.; Lian, Y.; Lu, L.; et al. Facing the challenges in ophthalmology clerkship teaching: Is flipped classroom the answer? *PLoS ONE* **2017**, *12*, e0174829. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
12. McLaughlin, J.C.; Griffin, L.M.; Esserman, D.A.; Dabidson, C.; Glatt, D.M.; Roth, M.T.; Gharkhlonarehe, N.; Mumper, R.J. Pharmacy student engagement, performance, and perception in a flipped satellite classroom. *Am. J. Pharm. Educ.* **2013**, *77*, 1–8. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
13. Muzyk, A.J.; Fuller, S.; Jiroutek, M.R.; O’Connor, C.; Butler, A.C.; May, D.B. Implementation of a flipped classroom model to teach psychopharmacotherapy to third-year Doctor of Pharmacy (PharmD) students. *Pharm. Educ.* **2015**, *15*, 44–53.
14. Ryan, M.D.; Reid, S.A. Impact of the Flipped Classroom on Student Performance and Retention: A Parallel Controlled Study in General Chemistry. *J. Chem. Educ.* **2016**, *93*, 13–23. [[CrossRef](#)]
15. Maarek, J.I.; Kay, B. Assessment of Performance and Student Feedback in the Flipped Classroom. In *American Society For Engineering Education (ASEE)*; American Society for Engineering Education: Seattle, WA, USA, 2015. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Clark, K.R. The Effects of the flipped model of instruction on student engagement and performance in the secondary mathematics classroom. *J. Educ. Online* **2015**, *12*, 91–115. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Jungić, V.; Kaur, H.; Mulholland, J.; Xin, C. On Flipping the classroom in large first year calculus courses. *Int. J. Math. Educ. Sci. Technol.* **2015**, *46*, 508–520. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Wilcox, R.R. *Introduction to Robust Estimation and Hypothesis Testing*; Academic Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2005.
19. Yuen, K.K. The two-sample trimmed t for unequal population variances. *Biometrika* **1974**, *61*, 165–170. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. Cortina Pérez, B.; Gallardo Vigil, M.A.; Jiménez Jiménez, M.A.; Trujillo Torres, J.M. Digital illiteracy: A challenge for 21st century teachers. *Cultura y Educación* **2014**, *26*, 231–264. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Trujillo Torres, J.M.; Cáceres, M.P.; Aznar, I. Análisis del uso e integración de redes sociales colaborativas en comunidades de aprendizaje entre la Universidad de Granada (España) y la Universidad John Moores (Reino Unido). *Revista Complutense de Educación* **2015**, *26*, 289–311. [[CrossRef](#)]

22. Chaves Barboza, E.; Trujillo Torres, J.M.; López-Núñez, J.A. Autorregulación del aprendizaje en entornos personales de aprendizaje en el Grado de Educación Primaria de la Universidad de Granada, España. *Phys. Rev.* **2015**, *8*, 63–76. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Porcaro, P.A.; Jackson, D.E.; McLaughlin, P.M.; O'Malley, C.J. Curriculum Design of a Flipped Classroom to Enhance Haematology Learning. *J. Sci. Educ. Technol.* **2016**, *25*, 345–357. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Trujillo, J.M.; Hinojo, F.J.; Aznar, I. Innovative and collaborative proposals e-learning 2.0 as a demand of the knowledge society. *ESE Educ. Stud. J.* **2011**, *20*, 141–159.
25. Williams, J.D.; Takaku, S. Help seeking, self-efficacy, and writing performance among college students. *J. Writ. Res.* **2011**, *3*, 1–18. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Olajide, J.K. Effect of Integrated Approach on Polytechnic Student's Achievement in Essay Writing. *J. Emerg. Trends Educ. Res. Policy Stud.* **2013**, *4*, 917–924.
27. Stathaakarou, N.; Scully, M.L.; Kononowicz, A.A.; Henningsohn, L.; Zary, N.; McGrath, C. MOOClearners' Engagement with Two Variants of Virtual Patients: A Randomised Trial. *Educ. Sci.* **2018**, *8*, 44. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Stöhr, C.; Adawi, T. Flipped Classroom Research: From “Black Box” to “White Box” Evaluation. *Educ. Sci.* **2018**, *8*, 22. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Rubia, B.; Guitert, M. Revolution in education: Computer support for collaborative learning. *Comunicar* **2014**, *42*, 10–14. [[CrossRef](#)]

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